

The Effect of Job Transfer on Employee Performance With Motivation and Job Satisfaction as Intervening Variables

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to provide empirical evidence of the effect of job transfer on employee performance with motivation and job satisfaction as mediating variables. The research population was 52, all of whom were tax inspectors at KPP Madya Malang Indonesia. All members of the population are used as samples. A total of 52 questionnaires were distributed to tax inspectors, and 36 questionnaires were returned, resulting in a response rate of 69.23%. The data analysis method used is path analysis. The results showed that job transfer did not affect employee performance. Furthermore, it was also found that motivation did not mediate the effect of job transfer on employee performance. Finally, this study found that job satisfaction mediates the impact of job transfer on employee performance.

KEYWORDS: Job Transfer, Motivation, Job Satisfaction, And Employee Performance

I. INTRODUCTION

Human resource management is the main factor in ensuring the achievement of good performance. Human resources are an essential asset and the main factor for the survival of an organization. The success of managing human resources is the key to the success of the organization. One of the efforts to manage human resources is to do job transfer. Job transfer encourages employees to work better in achieving higher careers. From an organizational perspective, job transfer is used to stimulate employees to unleash their potential, which impacts improving employee performance. Many previous researchers have conducted studies examining the effect of job transfer on performance, but the results are still inconsistent. Previous research found that job transfer affects employee performance (Saravani & Abbasi, 2013; Anitha, 2014; Rashki et al., 2014; Oparanma and I. Nwaeke, 2015; Mohan and Gomathi, 2015; Salih and Ibed, 2015, Akbari and Maniei, 2017; Muazza and Syarifuddin, 2017; Saravanan et al., 2017; Van Wyk et al., 2018, Tumipa and Rumokoy, 2018; Al-Romeedy, 2019; B. Ravikumar, 2020). Other researchers found that job transfer did not affect employee performance (Salih & Al Ibed, 2017; Jocom et al., 2017; Kampkötter et al., 2018).

The inconsistency of the prior research results regarding the effect of job transfer on employee performance indicates that there are other variables that affect the relationship between job transfer and employee performance. The other variables include work motivation and job satisfaction. Saravanan et al. (2017) stated that job transfer reduces the level of boredom which causes an increase in the level of employee motivation. Furthermore, Ajusa and Atambo (2016) indicated that job transfer improves employees' psychological and physical health by creating positive employee attitudes and job diversification by reducing boredom and being self-motivated towards their work. Shahzadi et al. (2014) revealed that job transfer motivates employees to work effectively. Work motivation is needed to maintain a high level of performance (Chen and Kao, 2014).

In addition to motivation, job satisfaction also has a mediating role in the relationship between job transfer and employee performance. Concerning the impact of job satisfaction on performance, Zanti (2015) has revealed that management seeks to implement job transfer to increase employee satisfaction. In addition, job transfer reduces fatigue in performing repetitive tasks every day, increasing job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is a positive feeling about one's job, which results from an evaluation of its characteristics (Robbins, 2013). An employee with high job satisfaction has positive feelings about the job, while dissatisfied people have negative feelings. Al-Romeedy (2019) states that job satisfaction has a role in the relationship between job transfer and performance.

Many previous studies examine job transfer, but only a few have been conducted in government organizations. Organizations often transfer jobs in an effort to develop existing human resources. These efforts are intended to provide opportunities for

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each employee to develop their knowledge and experience related to their position. Job transfer is hoped to reduce work saturation, and there will be a dynamic atmosphere in the organization that impacts job satisfaction and increased performance. Job transfer is also a routine activity in government agencies to implement the principle of the right man in the right place. Job transfer is often used as a reward and punishment so that every employee is motivated to work seriously under the established rules and avoid work irregularities. Job transfer is a career development step in increasing work to a higher level. The purpose of this study is to repeat previous research by examining the mediating effect of motivation and job satisfaction on the relationship between job transfer and employee performance in government organizations.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Many previous studies examine job transfer, but only a few have been conducted in government organizations. The Effect of Job Transfer on Employee Performance

Job transfer can increase the knowledge and abilities of employees in terms of quality and quantity. Job transfer also expands the scope of work that can be done and is a means to further develop employees. Employees will be encouraged to work better in achieving a higher career. From an organizational point of view, job transfer is used to stimulate employees to unleash their potential. Job transfer is a technique followed by organizations to improve the performance of workers and make them more committed to work (Mohan and Gomathi, 2015).

Job transfer affects employee performance. Performance is behavior with defined indicators that can be evaluated positively or negatively for employees. Origo and Pagani (2008) stated that the job transfer system effectively improves human resource performance and productivity. They claim that it is an effective option to facilitate and speed up operations, saving time and resources. Job transfer leads to increased productivity of human resources. It improves organizational performance by training multi-skilled employees, creating efficient, logical interaction between skills and motivation, and providing practical participation for employees whose biggest advantage is increased job satisfaction. Job transfer should be designed in such a way as to achieve maximum efficiency and effectiveness and the highest level of performance. Job transfer can result in mobility, new skills, new work environments, new social dialogues, new experiences, and new professional fields. In addition, job transfer also minimizes employees to do the same movement for a long period and increases morale and motivation.

The results of previous studies show that job transfer has a significant effect on employee performance (Rashki et al., 2014; Dhanraj and Parumasur, 2014; Muazza and Syarifuddin, 2017; Saravanan et al., 2017; Akbari and Maniei, 2017; Tumipa and Rumokoy, 2018; Ravikumar et al., 2020). Based on this explanation, the first research hypothesis is stated as follows:

H1: Job transfer affects employee performance

The Effect of Job Transfer on Employee Performance With Motivation as an Intervening Variable

Performance is the function of ability and motivation. Employee performance appraisal can be observed through the ability of employees to complete the assigned tasks according to their expertise, skills, and motivation. Performance measurement has three indicators of work productivity, namely quantity, quality, and timeliness. Employee performance can be measured by whether or not employees can carry out tasks according to provisions and standards.

There are two factors related to employee performance: the employee's willingness or motivation to work and the employee's ability to carry it out. According to Gomez (2003:177), performance is a function of motivation and ability. The ability is inherent in a person and manifested in his actions at work. At the same time, motivation is a very important aspect to drive one's creativity and ability to do a job and always be enthusiastic in carrying out work. Employees will be able to do the work and achieve maximum results. To achieve maximum performance, motivation is needed that can bring up the will and enthusiasm for work. Motivation serves to stimulate the ability of employees so that maximum performance results will be created.

Motivation mediates the relationship between job transfer and employee performance (Al-Romeedy, 2019; Ravikumar, 2020). Job transfer can lead to motivation for employees to do their jobs better, which in turn has an impact on improving employee performance. Based on this, the second research hypothesis is stated as follows:

H2: Job transfer affects employee performance through work motivation

The Effect of Job Transfer on Employee Performance With Job Satisfaction as Intervening Variable

Job satisfaction is an essential element in the field of management and organizational behavior. Job satisfaction is a collection of feelings and beliefs in work. Job satisfaction is a positive attitude that is believed to lead to high performance and reflect employees' feelings about various aspects of work.

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Job satisfaction is indicated to mediate the effect of job transfer on job satisfaction. Job transfer is one way to increase job satisfaction. Saravani and Abbasi (2013) and Al-Romeedy (2019) prove that job satisfaction can mediate job transfer with performance. Employees who are satisfied with implementing a work transfer because the physical and non-physical environment is good and transfers to places and positions that are in accordance with their wishes and according to their skills will be eager to work beyond what is expected. The higher the perceived benefits of a job transfer, the higher job satisfaction, which will further improve employee performance. Based on this, the third hypothesis of this study is as follows:

H3: Job transfer has an effect on employee performance with job satisfaction as an intervening variable.

Based on the development of the hypothesis above, the research model can be described as follows:

Figure 1. Research Model

III. METHODOLOGY

This type of research is quantitative causal research which aims to determine the effect between variables. This study uses primary data collected through a questionnaire. The population is the whole object of research and fulfills certain characteristics. The research population was 52, all of whom were tax inspectors at tax office Malang Indonesia. All members of the population are used as samples. A total of 52 questionnaires were distributed to tax inspectors, and 36 questionnaires were returned, resulting in a response rate of 69.23%.

Variable Operational Definition

1. Job transfer

Job transfer is the movement of the employee on the same job at a different location. Job transfer indicators are job saturation, additional knowledge, skills, and competencies, management preparation, choice of the right work position, and development of social relations.

2. Motivation

Motivation is an impulse that comes from within humans that activates, moves, and directs behavior to achieve goals. There are four (4) indicators of work motivation: physiological needs, safety needs, social needs, esteem needs, and self-actualization.

3. Job satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a positive feeling about one's job, which results from an evaluation of its characteristics (Robbins, 2008). The job satisfaction variable in this study uses four (5) indicators: loyalty, honesty, creativity, leadership, and salary levels.

4. Employee performance

Employee performance is the result of work in quantity and quality achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with his responsibilities. Employee performance measurement indicators are quantity, quality, timeliness, and effectiveness.

Analysis Method

The path analysis technique is used in testing the magnitude of the contribution indicated by the path coefficient on each path diagram of the causal relationship between variables. The structural equations of the paths are as follows:

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Equation 1: $Y1 = \alpha + \beta1X1 + \beta2Z1 + \beta3Z2 + \epsilon1$

Equation 2: $Z1 = \alpha + \beta1X1 + \epsilon2$

Equation 3: $Z2 = \alpha + \beta1X1 + \epsilon3$

Where:

Y: employee performance; a: constant; $\beta1, \beta2, \beta3$: Regression Coefficient; X1: Job transfer; Z1: Motivation; Z2: Job satisfaction; ϵ : error

To test the hypothesis, a significance level test of 5% (0.05) was used. If the significance value is higher than 0.05, a hypothesis is rejected, which means that the individual exogenous variables did not affect the endogenous variables. If the significance value is lower than 0.05, a hypothesis is accepted, meaning that the exogenous variables individually and significantly affect the endogenous variables.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Demographic Data of the Respondents

Table 1 below presents data on the background of the respondents consisting of gender, age, years of service, and education level

Table 1. Demographic Data of the Respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
<u>Age</u>		
• Between 30 – 40 years	8	22.22
• Between 41 - 50 years	28	77.78
<u>Gender</u>		
• Male	36	100
• Female	0	0
<u>Years of service</u>		
• Between 11 – 20 years	15	41.67
• Between 21 - 40 years	21	58.33
<u>Level of education</u>		
• Diploma	4	11
• Bachelor	18	50
• Master	14	39

Table 1 shows that the overall respondents are male. Table 1 also shows that the highest percentage of respondents aged 41 to 50 is 77.78%, respondents aged 30 to 40 years are 22.22%. Furthermore, 41.67% of respondents have tenure between 11 and 20, and 58.337% have tenure between 21 and 40 years. Finally, the highest percentage of respondents' education level is a bachelor (50%), master 39%. and diploma 11%

Hypotheses Testing

Following tables 2 and 3 are used to test the three hypotheses that have been developed above. Table 2 presents the regression results of the three structural equations, while table 3 presents the direct, indirect, and total effects.

Table 2. Regression Results

Structural equations	Variables	Beta	t	Sig.
$Y1 = \alpha + \beta1X1 + \beta2Z1 + \beta3Z2 + \epsilon1$	Job transfer	-0.100	-0.644	0.524
	Motivation	0.204	1.358	0.184
	Job satisfaction	0.650	4.231	0.000
$Z1 = \alpha + \beta1X1 + \epsilon2$	Job transfer	0.506	3.418	0.002
$Z2 = \alpha + \beta1X1 + \epsilon3$	Job transfer	0.540	3.745	0.001

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Tabel 3. Direct, Indirect, and Total Effects

Path	Direct	Indirect	Total
JF → EP	-0,100		
JF → M → EP		0,506 x 0,204 = 0,103	-0,100 + 0,103 = 0,003
JF → JS → EF		0,540 x 0,650 = 0,351	-0,100 + -0,351 = 0,251

The effect of job transfer on employee performance

Hypothesis 1 states that job transfer influences employee performance. Table 2 results show the significant value of the effect of job transfer on employee performance is 0.524, which means that Hypothesis 1 is rejected because the significance value is greater than 0.05 ($0.524 > 0.05$). Thus, there is no direct effect of job transfer on employee performance.

The effect of job transfer on employee performance with motivation as an intervening variable

Hypothesis 2 states that motivation mediates the effect of job transfer on employee performance. Table 2 shows the significant effect of job transfer on motivation ($0.002 < 0.05$). Furthermore, Table 2 also shows that the effect of motivation on employee performance is not significant ($p\text{-value} = 0.184 > 0.05$). Table also 3 shows that the total effect $<$ direct effect ($-0.100 < 0.003$). So, one of the two paths is not significant, and the total effect $>$ direct effect. So motivation does not mediate the effect of job transfer on employee performance. Thus, hypothesis 2 is rejected.

The effect of job transfer on employee performance with job satisfaction as an intervening variable

Hypothesis 3 states that job satisfaction mediates the effect of job transfer on employee performance. The p-value of the effect of job transfer on motivation is significant at 0.001, which is lower than the value of 0.05, as shown in Table 2. Table 2 further reveals that job satisfaction has a significant impact on employee performance ($p\text{-value} = 0.000 < 0.05$). Table 3 also reveals that the total effect is greater than the direct effect ($-0.251 > -0.100$). Because both paths are significant, and the total effect is greater than the direct effect, it can be concluded that work satisfaction mediates the effect of job transfer on employee performance. Hypothesis 3 is so accepted.

Discussions

The effect of job transfer on employee performance

The results of this study indicate that job transfer does not affect employee performance. The absence of the effect of Job transfer on employee performance suggests that employees who are transferred feel comfortable because there is no difference between the old workplace and the new workplace. The feeling of comfort arises because employees are placed in the same position, and the work environment is not much different from the old workplace. This is why employees' work motivation does not change when there is a change of place of work. The results of this study support the findings of previous researchers conducted by Saravani and Abbasi (2013), Salih and Ibed (2015), and Hampongo and Foya (2020). The researchers also found that job transfer had no effect on employee performance. The results of the study are not in line with the findings of previous researchers who found that job transfer had an impact on employee performance (Rashki et al., 2014; Mohan and Gomathi, 2015; Oparanma and I. Nwaeke, 2015; Muazza and Syarifuddin, 2017; Saravanan et al., 2017; Akbari and Maniei, 2017; Tumipa and Rumokoy, 2018; Van Wyk et al., 2018; Al-Romeedy, 2019; B. Ravikumar, 2020).

The effect of job transfer on employee performance with motivation as an intervening variable

This study shows that motivation does not mediate the effect of job transfer on employee performance. Job transfer within the Directorate General of Taxes has been routinely carried out. For tax examiners, moving from one place to another is common, so they feel comfortable even though they are working in a new location. Inspectors will feel comfortable in whatever city they are placed to work in. The results of this study are not in line with the findings of Saravani and Abbasi (2013) and Al-Romeedy (2019), and B. Ravikumar et al. (2020).

The effect of job transfer on employee performance with job satisfaction as an intervening variable

The results showed that job satisfaction mediates the effect of job transfer on employee performance. Job transfer can lead to increased job satisfaction and ultimately improve employee performance. This finding shows that job transfer has positive consequences for tax auditors. Job transfer can reduce work stress and boredom, gain new experiences, and have a broader perspective. These positive consequences provide opportunities for examiners to achieve higher careers, which has an impact on job satisfaction. The results of the study support the findings of Saravani and Abbasi (2013) and Al-Romeedy (2019) that job satisfaction mediates the relationship between job transfers and employee performance.

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V. CONCLUSIONS

This research resulted in three main findings. First, there is no direct effect of job transfer on employee performance. Second, motivation does not mediate the impact of job transfer on employee performance. Third, job satisfaction mediates the impact of job transfer on employee performance. The study results are expected to provide practical benefits for the Directorate General of Taxes as consideration for improving employee performance through job transfer. For future researchers, it is hoped that the results of this study can be used as a reference for research related to job transfers, motivation, job satisfaction, and employee performance in the context of public organizations.

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